

Dyeing Behavior of Banana Sap Treated Cotton Fabrics in the Presence of Reactive Dyes

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Abstract:

The textile chemical processing industry is a major contributor to environmental pollution. To reduce the environmental impact, an alternative approach is to incorporate bio-based substances in the dyeing process. In this study, banana pseudostem sap (BPS) solution was utilized due to its unique property of staining cotton material, which is challenging to remove and requires more washing. This characteristic was leveraged to treat the cotton fabric and assess its suitability for dyeing with reactive colors while minimizing the use of salt and other chemicals, thus reducing the overall effluent load. Fresh banana sap extract was collected, purified, and added to a reactive dye bath at varying concentrations and dyeing was continued for 60 minutes at 60°C. A total of 48 samples were prepared by keeping the temperature constant and examined under a spectrophotometer for the color strength values. Interesting results were obtained and show that material to sap ratio of 1:25 has a considerable influence on the color strength values out of other combinations. To further investigate the influence of temperature on the color uptake the temperature was varied and samples were developed. Spectrophotometric investigation on color strength observed that samples dyed at 80°C have a considerable impact on K/S values at material to sap ratio of 1:25 at a 50gpl concentration of salt.

Keywords: *Banana Pseudostem Sap, cotton fabric, effluent, reactive dyes, Spectrophotometric*

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1. Introduction

The textile chemical processing industry significantly contributes to environmental pollution, with nearly 70% of the total pollution stemming from the industry. Chemical usage in this industry has adverse effects on the environment and human health [1]. These chemicals, such as alkali, acids, surfactants, inorganic salts, and dyes, are present in the wastewater, leading to pollution [2]. Additionally, the high energy consumption in heating dye solutions exacerbates environmental problems [3-5]. Numerous approaches have been devised to minimize both energy and water consumption [6]. In cotton processing industries using reactive dyes, the discharged wastewater is highly polluted, with a heavy oxygen demand, salinity, and color. Treatment is crucial before releasing it into nearby water sources. However, due to high costs, many industries can't afford proper treatment. Advancements in chemical processing technology, like machinery design and eco-friendly auxiliaries, are necessary to reduce the wastewater load. Reactive dyeing in cotton consumes large amounts of water and salt, leading to salinity and the presence of alkali and organic matter in the wastewater [7].

Dye particles that remain attached to the fiber are considered fixed and create covalent bonds with the fiber. Under optimal dyeing conditions, approximately 50-80% of the dye is fixed to the fiber, while the remaining color is released into the effluent water [8]. Reactive dyeing of cotton necessitates a substantial amount of salt to aid in the exhaustion process, which varies based on shade depth, dye structure, and application method. The use of alkali depends on the dye type and pH requirements for dye fixation in the fiber. However, both the salt and alkali used in the process are non-biodegradable and toxic. Consequently, the wastewater remaining after dyeing contains these chemicals, along with high levels of biological oxygen demand, organic and inorganic solids [9, 10]. Researchers are exploring new technologies in the chemical processing of textiles to address ecological issues associated with

conventional dyeing systems. These systems typically require large quantities of water and chemicals, resulting in highly polluted wastewater. The aim is to develop methods that reduce the use of chemicals and water, improving the overall sustainability of the textile industry [11, 12]. Researchers have introduced various approaches in dyeing, including the use of reactive dyes without salt [12], pretreatment of cotton fabric with EDTA [9], treatment with chitosan and its derivatives [13], cellulose grafting with cationic agent [14], microwave-assisted low material to liquor ratio dyeing [15], natural dyeing using mordants [16, 17]. Banana pseudostem sap (BPS) is a plant extract rich in phenolic and aromatic amino compounds. It offers properties like permanent staining, antioxidants, and anti-bleeding. BPS shows promise as a fixation agent in textile dyeing, especially for mordanting cotton fabric with natural dyes. Previous research indicates enhanced fastness properties post-dyeing with BPS [18]. The primary objective of this study is to treat the pretreated cotton fabric with BPS and analyze its dyeing behavior using different concentrations of salt.

2. Materials & Methodology

2.1 Materials

The 100% bleached cotton fabric was selected for this study. Banana SAP was collected from the stem part of the banana tree and it was filtered and used without any further additions. Universal padding mangle was used to treat the cotton fabric with sap at 100% expression. Reactive dyes of Corafix Red ME3B was used to dye the cotton fabric supplied by Color Tex Industries Pvt. Ltd., Surat, India. Other chemicals like salt and soda ash of laboratory grade were used.

2.2 Methodology

To analyze the effect of SAP treated cotton fabric on the dyeing behavior with reactive dyes, the design of the experiment was planned and is given in Table 1. The samples to banana sap ratio varied from 1:15 to 1:125 and then dyed in the presence of reactive colors by changing the salt ratio from 10 to 70gpl. There is no water is used in the dyeing process except for the standard sample. The entire dyeing process was carried out using 20gpl soda ash at 60°C for 60 minutes. A total of 48 samples were developed, and the color strength values were compared with the standard samples by spectrophotometer.

Table 1 - Experimental design for dyeing of cotton fabric with Reactive dyes in the presence of banana SAP solution

Sr. No.	Sample Name	Material to Sap ratio	Dye Conc. in %	Salt Conc. in GPL	Soda Ash Conc.in GPL	Temperature in °C	Time in Min
1	Standard Sample S15W	-	2	70	20	60	60
2	Sap15 Salt10	01:15	2	10	20	60	60
3	Sap15 Salt20			20			
4	Sap15 Salt30			30			
5	Sap15 Salt40			40			
6	Sap15 Salt50			50			
7	Sap15 Salt60			60			
8	Sap15 Salt70			70			
Material Sap ratio		1:15, 1:25, 1:50, 1:75, 1:100, 1:125					
Reactive Dye type		Hot Brand dye					

2.3 Evaluation

The main objective of this work is to assess the banana sap treated cotton fabric and its suitability to apply reactive dyes onto it. Therefore, the treated fabrics were examined under a Premier color scan spectrophotometer for its color values and to optimize the best combinations.

3. Results & discussion

The dyeing experiments were designed in such a way that the cotton fabric was dyed with reactive dyes by varying material to sap ratios i.e., 1:15, 1:25, 1:50, 1:75, 1:100, 1:125 and also by varying the salt concentrations from

10gpl to 70 gpl as mentioned in Table 1. A total of 48 samples were developed and evaluated for the L*, a*,b*, and K/S values after soaping using a Premier color scan spectrophotometer 5100H at maximum wavelength, and the results are given in Table 2.

In the material-to-sap ratio of 1:15, a total of seven samples were developed by changing salt concentration and dyed with reactive dyes at 60°C for 60 min. The results were compared with a standard sample (S15W) developed with material to liquor ratio of 1:15. It was evident from the K/S results that there was no considerable effect of sap presence in the dye bath. Similarly, samples were developed with a material-to-sap ratio of 1:25 (25SP 10SL to 25SP 70SL) and compared with the standard sample (S25W). Interesting results were obtained in this combination. By increasing the salt content from 10gpl to 70gpl along with the sap content increasing pattern of K/S values was observed. The increasing pattern started early at 40gpl salt and in the presence of sap and continued. In the case of 50 gpl salt and 25 parts of sap (25SP50SL), the K/S value is 11.35, higher than the standard sample of 10.92. This is because the strong crosslinking of sap with cotton fabric results in more color uptake, even with low salt concentration [19]. This trend was not observed in other combinations of material to sap ratio i.e. 1:50, 1:75, 1:100 and 1:125 and might be due to an increase in material to sap ratio results in lower dye uptake.

Table 2 - L, a, b, and K/S values of banana sap treated cotton fabrics at varying salt concentrations

S. No	Sample Name	L*	a*	b*	K/S values
1	S15W	35.109	-8.992	-18.083	10.21
2	15SP10SL	33.172	-7.71	-14.144	3.98
3	15SP20SL	33.586	-8.29	-14.532	4.62
4	15SP30SL	34.515	-8.94	-16.325	5.84
5	15SP40SL	34.937	-9.23	-17.01	5.98
6	15SP50SL	35.049	-9.485	-17.087	6.98
7	15SP60SL	34.693	-8.408	-17.824	8.23
8	15SP70SL	35.021	-9.048	-17.952	10.54
9	S25W	34.466	-9.356	-17.994	10.926
10	25SP10SL	34.732	-9.605	-17.83	5.23
11	25SP20SL	34.565	-9.281	-18.293	7.92
12	25SP30SL	34.885	-9.703	-18.249	9.12
13	25SP40SL	34.443	-9.351	-18.19	10.243
14	25SP50SL	34.178	-8.952	-18.131	11.354
15	25SP60SL	34.273	-8.963	-18.315	11.804
16	25SP70SL	34.322	-9.155	-18.421	11.331
17	S50W	36.044	-9.564	-18.483	9.825
18	50SP10SL	32.436	-6.882	-12.062	4.52
19	50SP20SL	32.595	-6.613	-13.274	5.96
20	50SP30SL	33.403	-7.575	-13.965	6.32
21	50SP40SL	33.87	-7.932	-15.152	6.98
22	50SP50SL	34.466	-8.397	-16.083	7.82
23	50SP60SL	34.703	-8.074	-17.293	8.68
24	50SP70SL	35.051	-8.281	-18.198	9.12
25	S75W	37.013	-9.875	-18.499	9.208
26	75SP10SL	35.801	-8.687	-16.796	3.913
27	75SP20SL	36.711	-9.749	-17.558	5.439
28	75SP30SL	36.005	-8.979	-17.111	4.812
29	75SP40SL	36.397	-9.139	-17.951	6.439
30	75SP50SL	36.444	-9.353	-17.506	5.889
31	75SP60SL	36.195	-9.041	-17.764	6.237
32	75SP70SL	36.395	-8.926	-18.414	7.524
33	S100W	41.686	-10.361	-18.436	6.554

34	100SP10SL	37.238	-8.29	-7.101	2.109
35	100SP20SL	37.918	-8.565	-8.693	2.437
36	100SP30SL	38.772	-9.141	-10.794	2.734
37	100SP40SL	39.481	-9.648	-12.204	3.846
38	100SP50SL	39.686	-9.901	-12.427	3.767
39	100SP60SL	40.246	-9.882	-14.236	3.715
40	100SP70SL	39.959	-9.27	-14.74	3.03
41	S125W	40.638	-10.319	-18.345	7.05
42	125SP10SL	37.889	-7.838	-13.274	1.695
43	125SP20SL	38.222	-7.997	-14.261	1.747
44	125SP30SL	38.234	-8.267	-13.799	2.144
45	125SP40SL	38.119	-8.229	-13.897	2.496
46	125SP50SL	39.091	-8.931	-15.544	2.76
47	125SP60SL	39.633	-9.18	-16.554	2.737
48	125SP70SL	39.696	-9.364	-17.007	3.511

Note: S-Standard sample, SP-Sap solution, SL- Salt

The K/S value effect plot of dyed samples is depicted in Fig. 3. The illustration distinctly indicates that the influence of sap on K/S values initially leads to an increase in color strength up to a ratio of 1:25. However, beyond a 1:50 sap ratio, there is a decrease in color strength values. In contrast, the impact of salt on color strength values demonstrates a consistent increase pattern, as clearly depicted in the figure. The interaction plots for color strength values are shown in Fig.2. The interaction of sap & salt together leads to an increase in the color values then there is a drop in the color values. This may be due to the high Sap ratio leading to more dilution of dye particles and results in less exhaustion.

Figure 1 - Main effect plot for K/S values of dyed samples

Figure 2 - Interaction plots for K/S values in fitted means

All the results depicted from the designed experiment were conducted at 60°C temperature. Further, to analyze the effect of temperature on the dyeing behavior of cotton fabric in the presence of sap, trials were conducted at 60°C, 80°C, and 100°C by keeping a time of 60 min as constant. Also, the earlier studies found that the best results were obtained with a material-to-sap ratio of 1:25. So this combination was chosen for further investigations along with 1:50 and 1:75 for in-depth analysis. Accordingly, the design of the experiment was planned as given in Table.3, and a total of 27 samples were developed, and the results are given in Table. 4.

Table. 3 Experimental design for dyeing of cotton fabric by varying sap content, Salt and temperature

S. No.	Material to Sap ratio	Salt (gpl)	Temp. °C	Soda ash (gpl)	Time (min)
1	1:25	40	60	20	60
2		50	80		
3		60	100		
4	1:50	40	60	20	60
5		50	80		
6		60	100		
7	1.75	40	60	20	60
8		50	80		
9		60	100		
<i>Dyeing time: After adding soda ash, maintain 60 min time</i>					

It was evident from the results that the sample 50SL80T has shown a K/S of 11.14, which is close to the S25W at 80°C temperature. This means that temperature influences the dye uptake by the fiber in the presence of sap, even at low salt concentrations. It was also observed that increased temperature from 60°C to 80°C resulted in an initial rise in K/s value but again started reducing when the temperature increased to 100°C. Experiments were carried out at material-to-sap ratios of 1:50 and 1:75 while altering the temperature. However, as indicated in Table 2, minimal variations in the color strength values were observed. This observation strongly suggests that there is no notable impact when increasing the sap ratio beyond 1:25. This could be attributed to the fiber reaching its maximum dye uptake capacity.

Table 4 . Experimental results of varying material to sap ratio, dyeing time, and salt concentration

Material to Sap ratio	Sample name	L*	a*	b*	K/S
01:25	40SL60T	33.047	-8.721	-17.922	10.43
	40SL80T	33.051	-8.174	-18.629	10.51
	40SL100T	32.363	-7.935	-17.853	9.69
	50SL60T	33.224	-8.662	-18.168	11.02
	50SL80T	32.884	-7.699	-18.877	11.14
	50SL100T	31.884	-6.938	-18.33	10.593
	60SL60T	34.919	-8.301	-20.617	11.60
	60SL80T	33.837	-7.706	-20.51	11.71
	60SL100T	33.092	-6.904	-20.032	10.22
01:50	40SL60T	36.595	-9.341	-18.693	7.12
	40SL80T	36.059	-8.681	-18.039	8.72
	40SL100T	36.376	-8.984	-18.99	8.10
	50SL60T	36.97	-8.776	-19.803	7.49
	50SL80T	37.102	-8.95	-20.246	8.791
	50SL100T	35.892	-8.994	-17.963	8.41
	60SL60T	37.172	-8.509	-20.679	8.48
	60SL80T	36.906	-8.432	-20.096	9.12
	60SL100T	37.903	-8.767	-21.929	7.158
01:75	40SL60T	36.22	-9.091	-19.803	6.643
	40SL80T	36.038	-9.501	-18.808	7.543
	40SL100T	35.686	-8.998	-18.83	7.215
	50SL60T	36.372	-8.986	-20.171	5.923
	50SL80T	36.291	-9.16	-19.917	7.124
	50SL100T	36.205	-9.185	-19.72	6.941
	60SL60T	36.672	-8.626	-21.265	6.683
	60SL80T	36.537	-7.932	-22.316	7.287
	60SL100T	36.574	-8.279	-21.536	7.135

Note: SL- Salt concentration in gpl and T-Temperature in °C

Based on the results obtained from the experiments, it is clear that, sap has a considerably influence in the dyeing behavior of cotton fabric in the presence of reactive dyes even at reducing salt concentrations.

4. Conclusions

In this study BPS was collected and purified and used in the dyeing of cotton fabrics with reactive dyes. The dyeing was carried out with varying material to sap ratios i.e 1:15, 1:25, 1:50, 1:75, 1:100, 1:125 at varying concentrations of salt from 10gpl to 70 gpl. Temperature and time of the treatment was kept constant to understand the influence of sap in dye uptake. A total of 48 samples were developed and examined under spectrophotometer for its color values. Interesting results were obtained with a sap ratio of 1:25, 60 gpl compared to sample dyed at same ratio with water. Other combinations does not have much influence on the color strength. To further understand the influence of sap in dye uptake, temperature was varied at three stages i.e. 60°C, 80°C and, 100°C and studied the color strenght. Interesting results were obtained with varying temperatures in dyeing. The comprehensive study on dyeing with Sap solution demonstrates a notable absence of water usage, thereby markedly reducing the environmental pollution load. Furthermore, the utilization of BSP derived from waste resources exemplifies a sustainable approach within the textile industry. This study is dedicated to exploring the integration of bio waste resources into the reactive dyeing process, with the aim of diminishing salt content and consequently mitigating effluent discharge. Subsequent research avenues may delve into kinetic studies and computerized color matching analyses to offer novel perspectives on this matter.

References:

- [1] R.M.Christie, *Environmental aspects of textile dyeing*. Woodhead Publishing Limited, 2007. doi: 10.1111/j.1478-4408.1993.tb01499.x
- [2] N. A. Ibrahim, N. M. Abdel Moneim, E. S. Abdel Halim, and M. M. Hosni, "Pollution prevention of cotton-cone reactive dyeing," *J. Clean. Prod.*, vol. 16, no. 12, pp. 1321–1326, 2008, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2007.07.002
- [3] N. Mohammad, M. Arami, F. Mazaheri, and S. Rahimi, "Degradation of sericin (degumming) of Persian silk by ultrasound and enzymes as a cleaner and environmentally friendly process," *J. Clean. Prod.*, vol. 18, no. 2, pp. 146–151, 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2009.10.003
- [4] H. Li, W. Bao, C. Xiu, Y. Zhang, and H. Xu, "Energy conservation and circular economy in China's process industries," *Energy*, vol. 35, no. 11, pp. 4273–4281, 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2009.04.021
- [5] W. Jiang, Z. Yuan, J. Bi, and L. Sun, "Conserving water by optimizing production schedules in the dyeing industry," *J. Clean. Prod.*, vol. 18, no. 16–17, pp. 1696–1702, 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2010.07.004
- [6] K. Sawada and M. Ueda, "Enzyme processing of textiles in reverse micellar solution," vol. 89, pp. 263–269, 2001
- [7] W. Schramm and J. Jantschgi, "Comparative assessment of textile dyeing technologies from a preventive environmental protection point of view," *J. Soc. Dye. Colour.*, vol. 115, no. 4, pp. 130–135, 1999, doi: 10.1111/j.1478-4408.1999.tb00310.x
- [8] B. Smith, "Wastes from textile processing," *Plast. Environ.*, pp. 293–295, 2003
- [9] N. S. E. Ahmed, "The use of sodium edate in the dyeing of cotton with reactive dyes," *Dye. Pigment.*, 2005, doi: 10.1016/j.dyepig.2004.07.014
- [10] S. Ali, Z. Khatri, A. Khatri, and A. Tanwari, "Integrated desizing-bleaching-reactive dyeing process for cotton towel using glucose oxidase enzyme," *J. Clean. Prod.*, vol. 66, pp. 562–567, 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2013.11.035
- [11] D. Das, S. Bakshi, and P. Bhattacharya, "Dyeing of EDTA-Modified Cotton With Reactive Dyes," *Cloth. Text. Res. J.*, vol. 34, no. 3, pp. 196–206, 2016, doi: 10.1177/0887302X16652998
- [12] T. Aktek and A. K. M. M. Millat, "Salt Free Dyeing of Cotton Fiber- A Critical Review," *Int. J. Text. Sci.*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 21–33, 2017, doi: 10.5923/j.textile.20170602.01
- [13] X. X. He, S. Liu, and Z. J. Li, "The Effects of Chitosan on Dyeing Abilities of Cotton Fabric Dyed with Reactive Dyes," *Appl. Mech. Mater.*, vol. 310, pp. 13–15, 2013, doi: 10.4028/www.scientific.net/amm.310.13
- [14] N. Ristić and I. Ristić, "Cationic modification of cotton fabrics and reactive dyeing characteristics," *J. Eng. Fiber. Fabr.*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 113–121, 2012, doi: 10.1177/155892501200700408
- [15] M. Irfan, H. Zhang, U. Syed, and A. Hou, "Low liquor dyeing of cotton fabric with reactive dye by an eco-friendly technique," *J. Clean. Prod.*, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.06.300
- [16] G. R. Chilukoti, B. Venkatesh, and V. Sai Chandana, "Optimisation of dyeing and mordanting parameters on cotton fabrics treated with allium cepa as a natural dye source," *J. Text. Assoc.*, 2019, [Online]. Available: <http://www.scopus.com/inward/record.url?eid=2-s2.0-85066145626&partnerID=MN8TOARS>
- [17] T. Bechtold, R. Mussak, A. Mahmud-Ali, E. Ganglberger, and S. Geissler, "Extraction of natural dyes for textile dyeing from coloured plant wastes released from the food and beverage industry," *J. Sci. Food Agric.*, vol. 86, no. 2, pp. 233–242, 2006, doi: 10.1002/jsfa.2360
- [18] M. R. Repon, M. A. Al Mamun, and M. T. Islam, "Eco-friendly Cotton Coloration Using Banana (Musa Sapientum) Waste: Optimization of Dyeing Temperature," *Univers. J. Eng. Sci.*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 14–20, 2016, doi: 10.13189/ujes.2016.040102
- [19] B. Venkatesh and S. K. S. Kumar, "Assessing banana pseudostem sap-treated cotton fabric's physical characteristics: implications for reactive dyeing applications," *Biomass Convers. Biorefinery*, Feb. 2024, doi: 10.1007/s13399-024-05430-7